

CRITERIA FOR THE SELECTION OF INTERMEDIATE RAIL FASTENERS

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Anotation: This article examined the choice of intermediate rail fasteners, which are one of the main elements of the rail superstructure, and their types.

Keywords: rail, attachment, rail, load, sleeper, construction.

Entrance part: We are not mistaken if we say that the importance of the railway in the economy of Uzbekistan, which is currently developing rapidly. In the railway network, the status of intermediate rail fasteners, which are one of the road superstructures, and the basics of their choice are considered an urgent issue.

The following types of intermediate rail fasteners are common, which are most commonly used in World Railways:

- Fastclip attachment (Great Britain) produced by Pandrol company;
- Attachment "W - 14" produced by the company "Vossloh" (Germany);
- Attachment "e clip" produced by the company "Pandrol" (Great Britain);
- "Nabla" binder produced by Allevard Stedef, France;
- Attachment "DSA", produced by the company "allegard Stedef", France;
- "Rex Lok" binder, Australia.

Of these types of fasteners above, in countries with climates close to Uzbekistan (Saudi Arabia, Jordan, Iran, Iraq, Azerbaijan, Canada, South America, Scandinavian countries, Georgia, USA, Denmark, Germany, Finland, Egypt, Netherlands, etc.) will be used.

Within the framework of the program for the transition of intermediate rail

fasteners for reinforced concrete sleepers at JSC" Uzbekistan Railways", the following main criteria for their assessment and assessment are adopted in order to determine the competitive types:

- the pressure force value from one clamp to the rail should be around 9-12 kN;
- the attachment system is sufficiently checked, that is, it must be used for five years on the road where reinforced concrete sleepers are installed, with a load of 25 tons per shot and speed conditions of 100 km/h, and be suitable for the movement of various trains;

- the attachment structure must be operating in the range from – 40os to +48os in the shade of the ambient temperature;

- fastening elements, as far as possible, should be made of local materials;

- the attachment structure is obliged to be able to install and untie it even with low-skilled road monters using simple tools with minimal technical skills;

- reduction of temperature stresses on road tracks without circuit should be carried out in the shortest possible time in the existing types of fasteners;

- the attachment structure must be made up of a minimum number of components;

- the attachment structure should be suitable for use in rail chains and automatic lock sections;

- the attachment structure must have properties that keep it from being disassembled into beruxsat parts. It is imperative that its installation and download can be carried out only with the help of special tools;

- it is necessary that the attachment structure is suitable for use in the reinforcement of sweat rail types, as well as for the Coordination of the road width with the use of alternative components;

- it is desirable that it be possible to assess the degree of attachment of the rail bottom to the sleeper using a clamp simply by examining it, without a special measuring instrument or other device;

- the attachment structure must be able (capable) to work even under the

influence of dust and sand, as well as aggressive environment;

- the attachment structure should allow it to be initially installed in a reinforced concrete screed at a reinforced concrete screed production plant;

- the service life of the fastener is maximum, and the sleepers must be equal to the service life.

Two types of welded joints of intermediate rail fasteners, the name of which is given above, were experimentally installed on the roads of JSC "oty". The Vossloh Binder was installed and used in reinforced concrete sleepers manufactured by Bent-Fosslo JV (Kazakhstan), and the "Pandrol Fastclip" binders were installed and used in sleepers produced by the SWETRAK firm (Sweden). In both cases, the pressure force of the clemmas on the rail was at least 10 kN.

Figure 1. "Pandrol Fastclip" type rail attachment

1 – edge (edge) insulator of clemma; 2 – clemma; 3 – anchor element; 4 – clemma working condition fixer; 5 – rail under depreciation rack; 6 – side base insulator.

In the process of their use, the status of both rail fasteners and the upper device as a whole was controlled. As a result of the passage of the road measuring wagon, the condition was brought under control according to the plan and profile according to the width of the rail colony. As a result of the analysis of the use of the types of fasteners of the specified type, the possibility and reliability of their high level of performance was confirmed, as well as an approximate uniformity was determined by most of the comparative criteria under consideration.

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